

MiMonte Project - Activities report under WP2, activity 2.b

2.b: Public consultations

Public Consultation Pego

Date : 9th April 2026

Place : Biblioteca Pública Municipal, Pego

Time: 18:30-20:00

Number of Participants: 4 people

OBJECTIVE:

The objective of the public consultation was to raise awareness among local landowners about the importance of sustainable forest management and the opportunities it offers — both economically and environmentally. Representatives of PegoViu presented two collaborative agreement models available to participants: a 15-year forest management plan for their plots, and a 40-year reforestation plan, both designed to support landowners in stewarding their land more effectively while contributing to broader ecosystem conservation goals.

TARGET GROUP

Private land-owners in and around Pego who own abandoned lands.

OUTREACH:

We have engaged the community through the following channels:

- Email invites through Pego Viu network
- Publication through PegoViu's social media

METHODOLOGY

The meeting started off with a general introduction to the local natural environment, the impact of climate change, the recent fires that affected the area of reforestation and learned about the methods for sustainable land management and opportunities that could benefit both the abandoned plots and their landowners. Subsequently, the ground was left open for dialogue about landowners, specifically what were their concerns in taking action in their plots. Participants engaged in a meaningful conversation with mediators.

OUTCOMES

Despite a limited turnout — largely due to the Easter holiday, which prevented several interested participants from attending — the public consultation proved to be a success on multiple fronts.

First, the level of interest was encouraging: a significant number of people responded positively to the invitation but were unable to join due to prior commitments over the holiday period, expressing their regret and genuine interest in participating.

Second, those who did attend engaged actively in the discussion that followed the presentation, sharing their perspectives, raising questions, and contributing meaningfully to the debate.

Finally, the event yielded concrete outcomes. One attendee signed the 40-year agreement on the spot, while another expressed strong interest in signing the 15-year agreement. A third participant — although not a landowner — demonstrated a deep commitment to ecosystem preservation and

offered to contribute professionally as a university professor to PegoViu's work and to any current or future projects concerning this area.

GALLERY

Public Consultation Fuente La Reina

Date : 3rd April 2026

Place : Fuente la Reina

Time: 12:00 - 13.30hr

Number of Participants: 12

OBJECTIVE:

Familiarize people of Fuente La Reina with reforestation practices and forest management, so as to convince them to engage in forest management practices.

TARGET GROUP

People living in or owning land in Fuente La Reina

OUTREACH:

Municipality's Whatsapp channel; printed posters on public information boards and at the entry of the village bar; e-mails to participants of previous events; publication in online or facebook wall of <https://247valencia.com/> (<https://www.facebook.com/photo.php?fbid=1234956825286480&set=pb.100063165223229.-2207520000&type=3>); Whatsapps to participants of previous events; publication on Desert Leaves' Eventbrite page.

METHODOLOGY

The session included a live visit to the first reforested plot in Fuente la Reina, where project leader Wim Cambien presented the history of the project and the specific actions carried out. Two representatives of Asociación Agrícolaris (based in the neighbouring hamlet of Los Calpes) shared their experience of how landowners in their village successfully joined forces to collectively manage small agricultural and forest plots, directly encouraging Fuente la Reina residents to explore a similar model.

OUTCOME

12 residents gained direct knowledge of local reforestation efforts. Initial contacts were established between Fuente la Reina landowners and Agrícolaris representatives, with a view to potentially incorporating Fuente la Reina plots into the land managed by Agrícolaris.

GALLERY

Public Consultation - Ibiza

Date : 15th April 2025

Place : Ibiza

Time: 12:00 - 13.30hr

Number of Participants: 18

OBJECTIVE:

To bring together forest landowners to review technical forest management instruments and explore opportunities for collaboration with Regenera Natura toward promoting sustainable forest management.

TARGET GROUP

Forest landowners in the area.

OUTREACH:

Email

METHODOLOGY

The session consisted of a participatory meeting format in which technical forest management instruments were reviewed and presented. The possibility of collaboration with Regenera Natura was introduced as a framework for advancing sustainable forest management practices in the area.

OUTCOME

The session yielded a concrete result: the Rafal Trobat project, currently under active management by the organisation, emerged directly from this meeting. The session successfully engaged 18 landowners and opened a pathway for future collaboration with Regenera Natura.

GALLERY

